

1

cawiguanguasa' aq

2

nanwaq

3

lluq' akaq

4

niklliq

5

amartuq

6

qakiiyaq

2

Lake

1

Drone

4

**Red salmon/
sockeye**

3

**King salmon/
chinook**

6

**Silver salmon/
coho**

5

**Pink salmon/
humpback**

7

alimaq

8

weg'et

9

ek'illuni

10

et'uluni

11

meq

12

Quyanaa.

8

**Grass
(on land)**

7

**Chum/dog
salmon**

10

deep

9

Shallow

12

Thank you.

11

**Water
(freshwater)**

13

**nanwami
naulriit**

14

**mermi
naulriit**

15

iqalluk

**aquatic plants
(that grow in
fresh water)**

**Plants in
the lake**

Salmon